

CHANGES IN THE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF HYDROMORPHISM AROUND THE KATTAKURGAN RESERVOIR

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Abstract. *This study focuses on evaluating the impact of the Kattakurgan Reservoir's activity on the physico-chemical properties of the surrounding soils. According to the results, active hydro-morphism processes occur in the areas located near the reservoir due to the constant rise of groundwater levels. These processes have led to an increase in soil bulk density, a decrease in porosity, and a reduction in air exchange. In particular, in the northern-eastern parts (N-E -0.5 and N-E -1 profiles), the porosity was found to be moderate, while air exchange was weakened. In contrast, in areas farther from the reservoir (N-E-9, N-E -10, and background profiles), porosity was very good, and air exchange remained at an optimal level. Additionally, changes in the amount of micro aggregates in the soils were also investigated. The results showed that the proportion of micro aggregates smaller than 0.25 mm decreased in the areas close to the reservoir, which indicates degradation processes associated with hydromorphism and rapid fluctuations in soil moisture. Furthermore, the influence of the reservoir resulted in a decrease in the amount of organic matter, reduced microbial activity, and weakened aggregate stability. The findings demonstrate that changes in the water regime and physical structure of soils around the Kattakurgan Reservoir affect both soil fertility and ecological stability.*

Keywords: *reservoir, soil, hydromorphism, porosity, bulk density.*

INTRODUCTION

The granulometric composition of soils distributed around the Kattakurgan Reservoir has undergone significant changes under the influence of constant moisture and hydromorphism. As a result, the content of physical clay has increased from 43.1% to 59.7% (Abdullaev et al., 2020). Several researchers (Rzetala et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2018) have emphasized that the increase in physical clay content around reservoirs alters soil water permeability and aeration regimes. The main factor contributing to hydromorphism, the rise in physical clay content, and the deterioration of reclamation conditions in soils is the elevation of the groundwater table. In the study area, the groundwater level ranges between 85 and 155 cm. It was observed that in soil horizons where groundwater levels are higher, the physical clay content is greater. Similar findings were reported by Zhang et al. (2016), Arheimer and Pers (2017), and Foster et al. (2003), who noted that an increase in physical clay content around reservoirs negatively affects soil fertility. Furthermore, soils in reservoir-adjacent areas tend to experience increased salinization.

The continuous presence of easily soluble salts leads to their accumulation within soil horizons, causing salinity development. Studies conducted in other regions have also confirmed the relationship between rising groundwater levels and variations in physical clay content (Ma et al., 2022), as well as the observed increase in soil salinity (Gebrekidan et al., 2021). The heavier granulometric composition contributes to enhanced salt accumulation (Li et al., 2024; Hossain et

al., 2015). As the proportion of physical clay increases, the soil accumulates ions such as Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} , thereby intensifying salinization processes. The soil pH also varies under these conditions. For instance, hydromorphism promotes the reduction of iron, resulting in decreased soil pH (Salmi et al., 2025). Conversely, an increase in organic matter due to hydromorphism can lead to a neutral pH environment (Adhikary & Pal, 2025). Consequently, it can be inferred that the hydromorphic processes occurring around reservoirs lead to an increase in the proportion of physical clay, which in turn facilitates salt accumulation and elevates the degree of soil salinization. The concept and causes of hydromorphism have been extensively analyzed in the scientific literature. Classical studies highlight the chemical changes occurring in water-saturated (submerged) soils, particularly focusing on the reduction processes of iron and manganese and their relationship with Eh (oxidation–reduction potential) dynamics.

According to these sources, hydromorphism refers to the development of anaerobic conditions in soils due to prolonged or constant water saturation, where elements such as iron and manganese accumulate in reduced forms (Ponnamperuma, F.N., 1972). Several studies have also examined the transformation of organic matter in soils, including the composition of plant and microbial residues. In hydromorphic soils (especially in irrigated lands), reducing conditions caused by oxidation–reduction processes contribute to the specific accumulation of organic matter, which influences soil structure (Kögel-Knabner, 2002). Numerous scientific works have also addressed hydromorphism in the context of excessive moisture and irrigation agriculture, including issues of water balance and waterlogging. In regions with limited water resources, many studies discuss the challenges and opportunities in managing irrigation systems. Inefficient water use and poor drainage systems are among the key issues.

Improper management of irrigation regimes leads to increased soil water content, rising groundwater levels, and intensified hydromorphic processes (Qadir et al., 2003). Research has also focused on providing economic and agrotechnical recommendations for sustainable water resource management in irrigated lands. Properly designed drainage systems and groundwater control have been identified as key factors in reducing hydromorphism risks (Oster & Wichelns, 2003). Furthermore, several fundamental studies have examined the protection of soils from salinization in irrigated areas. These works scientifically substantiate the interrelationship between water balance, waterlogging, and soil salinity. It has been emphasized that excessive water supply and inadequate drainage not only strengthen hydromorphic conditions but also accelerate soil salinization processes (Hillel, 2000).

METHODS

During the research, the main objective was to determine the physical properties of the soils — namely, bulk density, particle density, and porosity. All analyses were conducted in accordance with international and national standards (FAO, 2006; O‘z DSt 1053:2006). The amount of microaggregates in the soil was determined based on the Savvinov method.

RESULTS

Due to the continuous rise and persistence of groundwater levels around the Kattakurgan Reservoir, hydromorphism processes actively occur. As a consequence, soil compaction increases, porosity decreases, and air exchange weakens. According to the results, such processes were not uniformly observed across the areas surrounding the reservoir (see Table – 1).

Table 1.

Changes in soil porosity, degree, and air exchange around the Kattakurgan Reservoir

Profile	Depth (cm)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Particle density (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)	Porosity level	Air exchange
North-Eastern Area						
N-E-0.5	0-12	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
	12.-38	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	38-92	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	92-120	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
N-E-1	0-21	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	21-57	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	57-112	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	112-165	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
N-E -2	0-36	1,39	2,65	47,55	Good	Adequate
	36-69	1,39	2,65	47,55	Good	Adequate
	69-108	1,42	2,65	46,42	Good	Adequate
	108-170	1,41	2,65	46,79	Good	Adequate
N-E -3	0-28	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	28-74	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	74-106	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	106-180	1,39	2,65	47,55	Good	Adequate
N-E -4	0-30	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	30-67	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	67-158	1,38	2,65	47,92	Good	Adequate
N-E -5	0-42	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	42-74	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	74-165	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-E -6	0-38	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	38-69	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	69-120	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	120-156	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-E -7	0-25	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	25-66	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	66-101	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	101-160	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
N-E -8	0-40	1,32	2,65	50,19	Good	Optimal
	40-87	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	87-124	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	124-165	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
N-E -9	0-38	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	38-84	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	84-95	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	95-145	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate

	145-170	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-E -10	0-42	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	42-69	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	69-88	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	88-135	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	135-168	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
Backgro und site FON	0-42	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	42-75	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	75-141	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	141-176	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	North West region					
N-W-0,5	0-15	1,49	2,65	43,77	Moderate	Weak
	15-35	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
	35-52	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
	52-63	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
N-W-1	0-20	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	20-32	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	32-50	1,49	2,65	43,77	Moderate	Weak
	50-62	1,45	2,65	45,28	Good	Adequate
	62-78	1,45	2,65	45,28	Good	Adequate
N-W-2	0-7	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	7.-27	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
	27-44	1,46	2,65	44,17	Moderate	Weak
	44-54	1,46	2,65	44,17	Moderate	Weak
	54-80	1,46	2,65	44,91	Good	Weak
N-W-3	0-30	1,38	2,65	47,92	Good	Adequate
	30-53	1,38	2,65	47,92	Good	Adequate
	53-75	1,39	2,65	47,55	Good	Adequate
	75-145	1,39	2,65	47,55	Good	Adequate
N-W-4	0-30	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	30-58	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	58-90	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	90-154	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-W-5	0-32	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	32-46	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	46-70	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	70-110	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	110-175	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
N-W-6	0-30	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	30-48	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	48-125	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	125-165	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
N-W-7	0-25	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate

	25-45	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	45-87	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
N-W-8	0-26	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	26-44	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	44-70	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	70-170	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
N-W-9	0-28	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	25-74	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	70-112	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	105-165	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
N-W-10	0-25	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	25-70	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	70-105	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	105-160	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
Backgro und site FON	0-27	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	27-72	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	72-110	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	110-165	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
Northerly region						
N-1	0-35	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	35-60	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	60-70	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
	70-120	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
N-2	0-38	1,46	2,65	44,91	Moderate	Weak
	38-58	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	58-96	1,47	2,65	44,53	Moderate	Weak
	96-125	1,48	2,65	44,15	Moderate	Weak
N-3	0-25	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	25-39	1,36	2,65	50,08	Very good	Optimal
	39-77	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-4	0-25	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	25-39	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
		1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
		1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N-5	0-27	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	27-49	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	49-66	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	66-166	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
N-6	0-28	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	28-51	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	51-65	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	65-125	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	125-158	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate

N -7	0-26	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	26-61	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	61-84	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	84-105	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
	105-161	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N -8	0-32	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	32-68	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	68-92	1,35	2,65	49,06	Good	Adequate
	92-123	1,36	2,65	48,68	Good	Adequate
	123-163	1,37	2,65	48,30	Good	Adequate
N -9	0-30	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Adequate
	30-61	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Adequate
	61-96	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	96-142	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	142-168	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
N -10	0-33	1,31	2,65	50,57	Very good	Optimal
	33-64	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	64-91	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	91-135	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	135-161	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
Backgro und site FON	0-31	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	31-64	1,32	2,65	50,19	Very good	Optimal
	64-92	1,33	2,65	49,81	Good	Adequate
	92-140	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	140-168	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate
	168-195	1,34	2,65	49,43	Good	Adequate

According to the data presented in the table, a reduction in soil porosity and weakening of air exchange were clearly observed in the soils of profiles N-E-0.5 and N-E -1, located in the north-eastern part of the KattakurganReservoir. In the subsequent profiles — N-E -2, N-E -3, N-E -4, N-E-5, N-E -6, N-E -7, and N-E -8 — the soils exhibited good porosity and adequate air exchange. In contrast, in the soils of N-E -9, N-E -10, and the background area, which are situated farther from the reservoir, porosity levels were good to very good, and air exchange was at an adequate to optimal level. In the north-western sector of the reservoir, this trend was even more pronounced. According to the results, soils from profiles N-W-0.5, N-W -1, and N-W-2 demonstrated moderate porosity and weak air exchange. In the subsequent profiles — N-W-3, N-W-4, N-W-5, N-W-6, N-W-7, and N-W-8 - the soils showed good porosity with adequate air exchange. However, in profiles N-W -9, N-W -10, and those from the background area, located farther from the reservoir, the influence of the water body was negligible.

These soils exhibited very good porosity and optimal air exchange, indicating stable physical conditions. Similarly, soil samples collected from the northern part of the reservoir displayed a comparable pattern. The soils in N-1 and N-2 profiles showed moderate porosity and weak air exchange, while those from N-3 to N-9 exhibited good porosity and adequate air exchange. In the Sh-9 profile and the background soils, porosity was found to be good to very good, and air exchange remained at adequate to optimal levels. Long-term observations also

examined changes in soil micro aggregate composition around the Kattakurgan Reservoir. The distribution of aggregates of 10 mm, 7 mm, 5 mm, 3 mm, 2 mm, 1 mm, 0.5 mm, 0.25 mm, and <0.25 mm fractions was analyzed. Results revealed that in the areas closer to the reservoir, the content of micro aggregates smaller than 0.25 mm had decreased significantly (see Table -1).

Table 1.

Changes in the content of soil micro aggregates around the Kattakurgan Reservoir

Samples	Microaggregates, mm								
	10	7	5	3	2	1	0,5	0,25	<0,25
N-E-1	33,40	8,67	9,87	16,95	17,15	11,86	1,40	0,20	0,50
N-E -2	15,63	5,81	8,04	21,34	24,58	19,78	1,69	2,79	0,89
N-E -3	24,52	10,97	9,18	15,57	15,45	16,06	4,25	3,92	0,34
N-E -4	18,15	6,66	7,52	43,07	3,76	10,81	1,72	7,41	1,83
N-E -5	20,10	7,94	8,93	14,02	17,37	19,35	4,35	4,22	4,09
N-W-1	29,71	6,12	9,82	19,01	19,01	12,42	2,94	1,13	0,33
N-W -2	21,97	5,54	9,41	20,29	20,71	16,00	2,36	3,45	0,52
N-W -3	22,15	8,25	7,21	32,03	17,72	10,97	0,84	1,46	0,05
N-W -4	19,26	4,99	5,86	12,72	28,34	27,79	0,35	0,59	0,39
N-W -5	20,00	7,64	6,97	10,45	12,02	24,28	1,91	12,1 2	5,27
N-1	17,46	5,57	8,15	19,29	24,94	22,78	1,00	1,16	0,42
N-2	26,59	6,95	7,68	11,46	15,61	20,07	3,05	8,17	0,98
N-3	27,49	8,68	13,97	12,97	13,88	11,77	9,86	1,00	1,00
N-4	24,40	6,45	10,87	20,35	18,23	18,35	1,38	0,83	0,06
N-5	16,45	10,19	11,78	16,24	17,52	19,43	2,34	3,29	2,76
Western	15,73	9,60	6,32	10,33	11,26	19,67	3,29	13,4 0	11,02
Southern	27,71	6,46	4,93	7,79	7,34	13,25	3,94	18,2 9	10,84

DISCUSSION

Under the influence of the Kattakurgan Reservoir’s activity, moisture remains within the soil layers, and at certain times its rapid loss is observed. As a result of this process, soil aggregates smaller than 0.25 mm are more prone to degradation processes. When moisture is present, the “hydrating” forces within aggregates become active, making disaggregation (the breaking apart of aggregates) easier. The periodic fluctuations of water levels near the reservoir — frequent rising and lowering of the water table — create cyclic wetting and drying conditions in the soil. These cycles can weaken the internal bonding strength of aggregates, since organic matter and microbial activity are highly moisture-dependent. During these fluctuations, microbial activity declines, decomposition of organic matter accelerates, and aggregates begin to detach from one another. In hydromorphic soils, organic matter content decreases, leading to a loss of aggregate stability. As a result, macro aggregates (>0.25 mm) become dominant, while micro aggregates break down and decrease in quantity. In areas near the reservoir, due to the constant fluctuation of water levels, strong erosion, dust formation, and leaching of fine soil particles into drainage channels are observed. These processes cause micro aggregates to fragment into smaller particles, ultimately leading to their loss.

The hydrological stresses induced by the reservoir — such as cyclic changes in water level, alternating wet and dry conditions, and variations in moisture regime — have contributed to the disintegration of micro aggregates. A lack of organic matter has reduced the soil’s ability to reform and stabilize these micro aggregates. Additionally, leaching of mineral binding agents (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and others) and changes in pH have intensified dispersion and aggregate breakdown. Samples collected near the reservoir (Sh-shq-1, Sh-shq-2, etc.) show lower contents of micro aggregates (0.25 mm and <0.25 mm), while those collected farther away (South, Western) contain significantly higher proportions of small aggregates (10% or more). These findings confirm the above analysis: micro aggregate content decreases near the reservoir as a result of moisture fluctuations, organic matter deficiency, and physicochemical dispersion. The changes in soil micro aggregate composition under the influence of the Kattakurgan Reservoir can therefore be explained by the following key factors (see Table-3).

Table-3

Factor	Impact
Water level changes	Soils near a reservoir are exposed to cycles of moisture and drought, resulting in the breakdown of aggregates.
Low organic matter	In areas close to reservoirs, plant biomass and the rate of their conversion into humus are low, resulting in unstable microaggregates.
Mineral component washing	As water is absorbed, binding ions such as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are washed away → the amount of micro aggregates decreases.
Mechanical erosion	In areas close to reservoirs, soils are subject to waterlogging, resulting in the loss of fine fractions.
Sedimentation	In areas far from the reservoir, microaggregates are protected, which increases the accumulation process of microaggregates.

Based on the above findings, it can be concluded that the amount of micro aggregates in soils located near the reservoir has decreased, which has led to the disruption of soil structure, an increased risk of erosion, and a decline in agronomic quality. To preserve soil micro aggregates, agro technical measures such as the application of organic matter and regulation of water level fluctuations are recommended.

CONCLUSION

The analysis results demonstrate that the morphological and ecological conditions of soils and vegetation communities surrounding the Kattakurgan Reservoir vary significantly. With increasing distance from the reservoir, soil moisture decreases, mineralization levels rise, and sandy layers become dominant in the soil’s mechanical composition. These changes directly affect vegetation cover — as the physical and chemical properties of the soil deteriorate, the density and diversity of plant species decline. Furthermore, the results reveal that the ecosystem relationships between soil and vegetation are highly complex and interdependent. A deeper study of the geochemical processes occurring in this area is crucial for establishing a solid scientific foundation for effective soil restoration and the preservation of biological diversity. The findings of this research can serve as a basis for developing practical recommendations aimed at preventing soil degradation, selecting appropriate plant species, and organizing effective eco-restoration measures

in the areas surrounding the Kattakurgan Reservoir. Ultimately, these efforts will contribute to ensuring regional ecological stability and promoting the sustainable use of natural resources.

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